

The Impact of Learning Facilities and Learning Discipline for the Result Grade VII SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar

Ivan Rivaldo Purba^{1*}, Anton Luvi Siahaan², Sotarduga Sihombing³

Universitas HKBP Nommensen Pematang Siantar, Indonesia

Corresponding Author: Ivan Rivaldo Purba ; purbaivan123@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Learning facilities, Learning discipline, Study for result

Received : 7, September

Revised : 16, October

Accepted: 27, November

©2023 Purba, Siahaan, Sihombing. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

This research aims to find out how learning facilities and discipline influence the learning outcomes of class VII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. The variables in this research are learning facilities and discipline as independent variables and learning outcomes as dependent variables. This type of research is quantitative descriptive research, with a population of all class VII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar totaling 222 . students and the research sample was 145 students selected using *random sampling* techniques . Data collection techniques use observation and questionnaires, while data analysis techniques use validity tests, reliability tests, normality tests, multicollinearity tests, heteroscedasticity, multiple linear regression, t tests, f tests, and coefficient of determination tests (R²). The results of this research indicate that there is no positive and significant influence between learning facilities on the learning outcomes of class VII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar as seen from the $t_{count} < t_{table}$ or $1.032 < 1.6556$. There is a positive and significant influence between learning discipline on the learning outcomes of class VII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar as seen from the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ or $3.338 > 1.6556$. There is a positive and significant influence between learning facilities and discipline on the learning outcomes of class VII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar as seen from the $f_{count} > f_{table}$ value or $6.416 > 3.06$ and the significant value is $0.001 < 0.05$.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the learning of knowledge, skills and habits of a group of people that is passed on from one generation to the next through teaching, training or research. Education often occurs under the guidance of others, but it is also possible to be autodidactic. The National Education System is an effort made by the Indonesian government to educate the nation.

Learning facilities are learning aids that can be used to help students carry out the learning process so that learning activities become more efficient and effective. As stated by S. Nasution (2005:76), to improve the quality of teaching it must be supported by various facilities, learning resources and supporting staff, among others, sufficient resources and tools are needed to enable students to learn individually. Among other things, sufficient resources and tools are needed to enable students to learn individually. If good learning facilities are available at UPTD SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar , students will be better at studying. To be able to study well, among other things, a student needs a writing desk, chair and textbooks.

Apart from learning facilities, there are also other factors that influence student learning outcomes, namely learning discipline. Learning discipline factors also play an important role in student learning outcomes. Study discipline includes aspects such as consistent attendance, regularity in doing assignments, focus and concentration in the learning process, and good time management. Students who have good study discipline tend to have better learning performance because they can optimize their time and energy to study effectively.

In terms of problems encountered during initial observations, it is hoped that an educator must be able to have the ability to modify and develop the learning process so that the results obtained also increase. One of them is by improving the learning process by improving learning facilities and discipline in order to achieve better results.

Based on the scores obtained from the results of observations at SMP NEGERI 7SIANTAR, information was obtained that the Daily Test Assessments in the social studies subject class VII-1 were classified as diverse, some got high scores, some got medium marks and some got low scores. This can be seen from the Daily Test Assessment. In accordance with the opinion of Djamarah (2010: 108), which states that the implementation of learning is said to be successful if 75% or more of the number of students who take part in the learning process have reached the KKM. Furthermore, according to E. Mulyasa (2017: 130), states that the success of the class is seen from the number of students who are able to complete or achieve the KKM of at least 71%. If seen from the results of the students who succeeded in reaching the KKM, it was 47% and those who did not succeed in reaching the KKM was 53%. .

Based on the problems that have been described, the researcher is interested in conducting research with the title " **The Impact of Learning Dacilities and Learning Discipline for the Result Grade VII SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar** ".

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1. Learning Facilities

Learning facilities are learning tools that are used by teachers when teaching and that are used by students to receive the learning material being taught. Learning facilities are the facilities a0d infrastructure that must be available to facilitate educational activities in schools. According to E. Mulyasa (2004:49),

Explains that learning facilities are equipment and supplies that are directly used and support the educational process, especially in the teaching and learning process, such as buildings, classrooms, books, libraries, laboratories, tables, chairs, and tools and other teaching media. As stated by S. Nasution (2005:76), that to improve the quality of teaching it must be supported by various facilities, learning resources and supporting staff, among others, sufficient resources and tools are needed to enable students to learn individually.

2. Learning Discipline

A condition that is created and formed through the process of efforts made by a person to obtain a new change in behavior as a whole, as a result of his own experience in interaction with his environment which shows the values of obedience, compliance, loyalty, regularity and order. According to Subari in Dewi Anggraini's Journal (2020:46), discipline is obeying a rule with one's own awareness to create the goal of that rule. Based on the definition above, discipline can be seen from students' obedience to the rules (rules) relating to study hours at school, which include school entry and exit hours, student compliance in dressing, student compliance in participating in school activities, and so forth. All student activities whose compliance is seen are related to educational activities at school.

3. Learning outcomes

Learning outcomes have an important meaning in the teaching and learning process at school, which is a benchmark for success in the teaching and learning process. A person's mastery of learning outcomes can be seen from his behavior, both behavior in the form of mastery of knowledge and thinking skills. Hamalik (2008:155), learning outcomes are changes in behavior in a person that can be observed and measured in the form of knowledge, attitudes and skills. This change can be interpreted as an improvement and better development before those who didn't know became those who knew.

METHODS

The type of research carried out is descriptive quantitative research. This research is descriptive research because it aims to describe the facts and characteristics of a particular population or area in a systematic, factual and thorough manner. According to Sugiyono (2018:13), quantitative data is a research method based on positivistic (concrete data), research data in the form of numbers that will be measured using statistics as a calculation test tool, related to the problem being studied to produce a conclusion. Positivistic philosophy is used in certain populations or samples. The type of research used in this research uses questionnaire research.

According to Sugiyono (2017: 142), a questionnaire is a data collection technique that is carried out by giving a set of questions or written statements to respondents to answer

Based on the researcher's title " The Impact of Learning Facilities and Learning Discipline for the Result Grade VII SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar " . This research was carried out at SMPN 7 Pematang Siantar starting in June 2023 . The population in this study were all students of class VII SMPN 7 Pematang Siantar class VII-1 to class VII- 7 which totaled 222 students . The samples in this research were class VII- 1 with 21 students, class VII-2 with 21 students, class VII-3 with 19 students, class VII-4 with 21 students, class VII-5 with 21 students, class VII-6 as many as 21 people, and VII-7 as many as 21 students . So the total number of samples is 145 students.

RESULTS

Result

Instrument Validity Test

The validity test in this research used SPSS version 21 and Ms. Excel 2007. The level used to test the validity of the instrument is 0.05%. Based on the results of the validity test tested in class VII UPTD SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar with a total of 35 students .

The statement item is declared valid if the calculated r value $\geq r$ table with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. From the results of the validity test, it can be seen that the correlation between each question item and the total score of $n = 35$ shows that the r table is 0.334. This means that if the correlation value is more than 0.334 then the question is considered valid. The statement items that will be used when testing the hypothesis are only valid statement items, while invalid items cannot be used in research.

Table 1 Learning Facility Validity Test Results (X1)

Statement	r-count	r-table	Decision
1	0,734	0,334	VALID
2	0,746	0,334	VALID
3	0,535	0,334	VALID
4	0,549	0,334	VALID
5	0,842	0,334	VALID
6	0,463	0,334	VALID
7	0,827	0,334	VALID
8	0,696	0,334	VALID
9	0,654	0,334	VALID
10	0,459	0,334	VALID
11	0,842	0,334	VALID
12	0,576	0,334	VALID
13	0,827	0,334	VALID
14	0,746	0,334	VALID
15	0,535	0,334	VALID
16	0,842	0,334	VALID

Based on the statements from table 1, it shows that the 16 statements for Learning Facilities (X1) are all said to be valid because the test results show that $r_{hitung} > r_{tabel}$.

Table 2 Learning Discipline Validity Test Results (X2)

Statement	r-count	r-table	Decision
1	0,934	0,334	VALID
2	0,677	0,334	VALID
3	0,677	0,334	VALID
4	0,343	0,334	VALID
5	0,934	0,334	VALID
6	0,705	0,334	VALID
7	0,934	0,334	VALID
8	0,509	0,334	VALID
9	0,516	0,334	VALID
10	0,642	0,334	VALID
11	0,934	0,334	VALID
12	0,472	0,334	VALID
13	0,465	0,334	VALID

14	0.934	0.334	VALID
15	0.677	0.334	VALID
16	0.934	0.334	VALID

Based on the statements from table 2, it shows that the 16 statements for Learning Facilities (X1) are all said to be valid because the test results show that $r_{hitung} > r_{tabel}$.

Instrument Reliability Test

For the questionnaire reliability criteria, if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ with a significant level ($\alpha = 0.05$) then the questionnaire is said to be reliable. However, if $r_{count} \leq r_{table}$ then the questionnaire is considered to have no reliability. If the *Cronbach Alpha value* is > 0.60 it is said to be reliable, but if the *Cronbach Alpha value* is < 0.60 it is said to be unreliable.

From the data obtained, it is known that the *Cronbach Alpha* obtained was $0.935 > 0.60$. From the results of calculating the reliability of Learning Facilities, it can be concluded that the research instruments used are reliable.

From the data obtained, it is known that the *Cronbach Alpha* obtained was $0.940 > 0.60$. From the results of the Learning Discipline reliability calculation, it can be concluded that the research instruments used are reliable.

Classic assumption test Data Normality Test

Figure 1 Normal Probability P-Plot Graph

The test results can be seen in Figure 1. The P-Plot graph shows the conclusion that the data is spread around the diagonal line, so the data is declared normal.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 4 Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients ^a

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
LEARNIN G FACILITIE S	,994	1,006
LEARNING DISCIPLINE	,994	1,006

a. Dependent Variable: LEARNING OUTCOMES

The assumptions of the *Tolerance* and *Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)* can be stated as follows:

1. If $VIF > 10$ and *Tolerance* value < 0.10 then multicollinearity occurs.
2. If $VIF < 10$ and *Tolerance* value > 0.10 then multicollinearity does not occur.

The test results shown in table 4.5 show that *Tolerance* is > 0.10 and *Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)* < 10 , so it can be concluded that the data does not have symptoms of multicollinearity.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 2 Heteroscedasticity Test Results

From the image above in the scatterplot graph, it can be seen that the points are spread randomly above and below the number 0 on the X axis (*studentized residual regression*). And to the right and left of the number 0 on the Y axis (*regression standardized predicted value*). It can be concluded that based on the heteroscedasticity test using graphic analysis, the regression model formed is stated that heteroscedasticity does not occur (under conditions of homoscedasticity).

Hypothesis testing
Multiple Linear Regression Test

Table 4 Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	50,552	4,860		10,401	,000
LEARNING FACILITIES	,069	,067	,083	1,032	.304
LEARNING DISCIPLINE	,213	,064	,269	3,338	,001

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the constant value (a value) is 50,552 and for the learning facilities value (b1) it is 0.069 and for the learning discipline value (b2) it is 0.213 so that the multiple linear regression equation can be obtained as follows:

$$Y = a + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

$$Y = 50,552 + 0.069 X_1 + 0.213 X_2 + 4.860$$

Furthermore, this equation can be interpreted as follows:

1. Constant value (a) is 50.552
This means that a constant of 50.552 means that the consistent value of the learning outcome variable is 50.552
2. The regression coefficient X1 is 0.069 and X2 is 0.213. The regression coefficient is positive, so it can be concluded that the influence of variables X1 and variable X2 on Y is positive.

Partial Test (t Test)

Table 5 Partial Test Results (t Test)
Coefficients ^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	50,552	4,860		10,401	,000
LEARNING FACILITIES	,069	,067	,083	1,032	.304
LEARNING DISCIPLINE	,213	,064	,269	3,338	,001

From the table above it can be seen that the t test results for the Learning Motivation variable (X₁) show a calculated t value of 1.032 and a significance value of 0.304. Thus the calculated t value > t table (1.032 < 1.6556) and the sig value (0.304 > 0.05). This means that H1 is rejected, which means it does not exist The influence of learning facilities on the learning outcomes of class VII students in social studies subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar.

Meanwhile, the results of the t test for the Learning Discipline variable (X_2) show a calculated t value of 3.338 and a significance value of 0.001 . Thus the calculated t value $< t_{table} (3,338 > 1,6556)$ and the sig value ($0,001 < 0.05$). This means that H2 is accepted, where the learning discipline variable (X_2) has an influence on the learning outcomes of class VII students in social studies subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar.

Simultaneous Test (F Test)

Table 6 Simultaneous Test Results (f Test)

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1016.563	2	508.281	6.416	.002 ^b
Residual	11248.775	142	79.217		
Total	12265.338	144			

calculated F value is 6.416 and the sig value is 0.002. Thus the calculated $F > F_{table} (6.416$

$> 3.06)$ and the sig value ($0.002 < 0.05$) . This means that H3 is accepted where together there is an influence of Learning Facilities and Learning Discipline on the Learning Outcomes of Class VII Students in Social Sciences Subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar .

Coefficient of Determination Test (R2)

Table 7 Coefficient of Determination Test Results (R2)

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.288 ^a	.083	.070	8,900

a. Predictors: (Constant), LEARNING DISCIPLINE, LEARNING FACILITIES

b. Dependent Variable: LEARNING OUTCOMES

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the coefficient of determination in this study is an R square value of 0.083 . The coefficient value of 0.083 is equal to 8,30

%. This value means that the independent variables of learning facilities and learning discipline contribute an influence of only 8.3 % to the learning outcomes of class VII students in social studies at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar . Meanwhile, 91,70% are influenced by other variables not discussed in this research such as parenting patterns, learning motivation, school environment, teacher competence, etc.

Discussion

The purpose of this research is to see whether there is an influence between learning facilities and learning discipline on student learning outcomes. This research was carried out at UPTD SMP NEGERI 7 PEMATANG SIANTAR where the target of this research was students in grades VII 1-VII 7.

Learning facility and learning discipline variables are measured or scrutinized based on the results of answers to questionnaires distributed to students, while student learning outcome variables are obtained from the PTS scores obtained by students. The questionnaire/questionnaire distributed consisted of 32 statements which were answered by students and then the data was processed by researchers.

Data analysis test, namely the data normality test is said to be normal if the significance value is > 0.05 , while the research data output results for the normality test are with a value of 0.540. So it can be concluded that the significance value is $0.540 > 0.05$, meaning that the existing variables are normally distributed.

In the multicollinearity test model, it is said that a good regression model should not have any correlation between independent variables. If the independent variables are correlated with each other then the variable has a value of zero. The output results can be seen that the *tolerance value* of the independent variable is 0.994 and the VIF value of the independent variable is 1.006. Based on the *tolerance value* of $0.956 > 0.10$, it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables. And the VIF value is $1.006 < 10$. This means that there is no multicollinearity between independent variables.

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in the regression model there is inequality of variance and residuals from one observation to another. The output results can be seen in the scatterplot graphic image, showing that the points are spread randomly above and below the number 0 on the X axis (*studentized residual regression*). And to the right and left of the number 0 on the Y axis (*regression standardized predicted value*). It can be concluded that based on the heteroscedasticity test using graphic analysis, the regression model formed is stated that heteroscedasticity does not occur (under conditions of homoscedasticity).

The output results obtained in the multiple linear regression analysis obtained a constant value (a value) of 50.552 and for the learning facilities value (b1) of 0.069 and for the learning discipline value (b2) of 0.213, so the regression equation is:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_n X_n + e$$
$$Y = 50.552 + 0.069X_1 + 0.213X_2 + 4.860$$

A constant of 50.553 means that the consistent value of the learning outcome variable is 50.552. The regression coefficient X1 is 0.069 and X2 is 0.213. The regression coefficient is positive, so it can be said that the direction of influence of variables X1 and Variable X2 on Y is positive.

The t test results for the Learning Facilities variable (X₁) show a calculated t value of 1.032 and a significance value of 0.304. Thus the $\text{calculated t value} > \text{t table}$ ($1.032 < 1.6556$) and the sig value ($0.304 > 0.05$). This means that H1 is rejected, which means there is no influence of Learning Facilities on the Learning Outcomes of Class VII Students in Social Sciences Subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. Meanwhile, the results of the t test for the Learning Discipline variable (X₂) show a calculated t value of 3.338 and a significance value of 0.001.

Thus the calculated t value $< t_{table}$ ($3.338 > 1.6556$) and the sig value ($0.001 < 0.05$). This means that H_2 is accepted, where the learning discipline variable (X_2) has an influence on the learning outcomes of class VII students in social studies subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar.

calculated F value is 6.416 and the sig value is 0.002 . Thus the calculated $F > F_{table}$ (6.416 > 3.06) and the sig value is ($0.002 < 0.05$). This means that H_3 is accepted where together there is an influence of Learning Facilities and Learning Discipline on the Learning Outcomes of Class VII Students in Social Sciences Subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar.

The coefficient of determination is a measuring tool used to assess how well the model used is to explain the existing dependent variable. The results of this research output obtained an R Square value = 0.083 or 8.30 % . So the conclusion that can be

drawn is that the magnitude of the influence of the variables learning facilities (X_1) and learning discipline (X_2) on student learning outcomes (Y) is 0.083 (8.30%).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research results and discussion in chapter IV, the conclusions that can be put forward in this research are as follows:

1. There is no positive and significant influence between Learning Facilities on the learning outcomes of class VII students in the Social Sciences subject at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. This can be seen from the results of partial calculations (t test) in the learning environment (X_1) carried out using SPSS version 21, which shows the calculated t value $< t_{table}$ ($1.032 < 1.6556$) and significant value ($0.304 > 0.05$).
2. There is a positive and significant influence between Learning Discipline on the Learning Outcomes of Class VII Students in Social Sciences subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. This can be seen from the results of partial calculations (t test) on Learning Discipline (X_2) carried out using SPSS version 21, which shows the calculated t value $> t_{table}$ ($3.338 > 1.6556$) and significant value ($0.001 < 0.05$).
3. There is a positive and significant influence between Learning Motivation and Learning Facilities on Class VII Student Learning Outcomes in Social Sciences Subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. This can be seen from the results of simultaneous calculations (F test) on Learning Facilities (X_1) and Learning Disciplines (X_2) carried out using the SPSS version 21, namely, shows the calculated f value $> f_{table}$ ($6.416 > 3.06$) and a significant value ($0.001 < 0.05$).

FURTHER STUDY

Due to the limitations of this research, it is hoped that future research will be more in-depth in exploring information and preparing instruments. So that more facts can be revealed that underlie the influence of learning facilities and learning discipline on student learning outcomes.

The author realizes that in writing this thesis, there are still many shortcomings. For this reason, with all humility the author hopes for suggestions and constructive criticism for the perfection of writing this thesis research proposal in the future so that it can provide direction to the author in the next steps of writing.

REFERENCES

- Anggraini, Dewi. 2020. Discipline and Learning Achievement of Class VII Students at SMP Negeri 2 Kuantan. *Journal Al-Taujih*, Vol, 6. No 1:44-54.
- Arikunto. 2010. *Research Procedures: A Practical Approach*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Cipta. Cynthia Camellia Lela. et al. 2016. The Influence of Learning Facilities and Learning Motivation on Learning Achievement in Economics Subjects of Class XI IIS Students at SMA Negeri 5 Surakarta FY 2015/2016. *Journal*,
- Djamarah. 2010. *Teaching and Learning Strategies*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta. 2017. *Teaching and Learning Strategies*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta
- Ghozali, Imam. 2009. *Application of Multivariate Analysis with the SPSS Program*. Semarang : UNDIP. 2016. *Application of Multivariate Analysis with Programs*. IBM SPSS 23 (8th Edition). Printing VIII. Semarang: Publishing Agency. 2018. *Application of Multivariate Analysis with the IBM SPSS Program*. 25. Semarang: Diponegoro University Publishing Agency.
- Gie, The Giang. 2002. *Efficient Ways to Learn*. Yogyakarta : Gajah Mada University Press.
- Hamalik. 2008. *Teaching Planning Based on Approach*. System. Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksara.
- Hidayana, F, Avita. 2021. The Effect of Complete Learning Facilities on Mathematics Learning Outcomes of Class V Mi Nurul Ulum Madiun Students. *Paradigm Journal*, Vol, 11. No 1:190.
<https://ejournal.mandalanursa.org/index.php/IIME/article/download/3313/2571>
<https://ejournal.uinib.ac.id/jurnal/index.php/attaujih/article/view/1752>
<https://jurnal.uns.ac.id/bise/article/download/17966/14340>
<https://jurnal.untan.ac.id/index.php/jpdpb/article/view/23189>
<https://www.jptam.org/index.php/jptam/article/view/4469>
<https://www.staimmgt.ac.id/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/10.-PENGARUH-KELENGKAPAN-FASILITAS-BELAJAR.pdf>.
- Jaya. Suharsono. 2018. Student Perceptions of Factors that Influence Learning Discipline in Class XI Students. *Journal of Theory and Application*. Vol, 7 No. 3. <https://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/jbk/article/view/19535>
- Krisnayanti Heni Anggela Ayu Ga I. Wijaya Sandi. 2022. The Influence of Teacher Performance on Student Learning Outcomes for Class 5 Elementary School Science Subjects at XYZ School. *Mandala Education Scientific Journal*, Vol 8. No.2:5.

Larendra Brebes. *Pulpit Ilmu Journal*, Vol, 24 No

<https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/MI/article/view/21279>

Mulyasa, E. 2004. *Management Based School* . Bandung: Rosyada Karya Youth.2017. *Competency-based curriculum. Bandung: Teenagers.*

Naryanto . 2022. *The Influence of Learning Discipline and Family Environment on Learning Achievement. Banjaran: Eureka Media Aksara.*

Nasution , S. 2005. *Various Approaches in the Teaching and Learning Process.* Jakarta :PT. Literary Earth.

Nurhasanah. et al. 2017. *The Relationship between Discipline, Independent Attitude and Interest in Learning with Social Science Learning Outcomes in Elementary Schools. Journal of Education and Learning, Vol, 6 No 12.*

Pulungan Intan. Istirani. 2015. *Encyclopedia of Education* . Medan

Purwanto. 2017. *Evaluation of Learning Outcomes* . Yogyakarta: Learning Library.

Ridho, Sapirman. 2022. *Discipline level of children who take part in scouting and those who do not take part in scouting at SMA Negeri 3 Batanghari. Journal of Scientific Articles , Vol, 6. No 3:51.*

Sanjaya . 2009. *Learning Strategies Oriented to Educational Process Standards* . Jakarta:Kencana.

Siregar, Nurliani. 2015. *Education Profession. Pematangsiantar: HKBP Nommensen University*

Slameto. 2013. *Learning Facilities and Factors That Influence Them* . Jakarta: PT. Rineka Cipta.

Sugiarto. et al. 2019. *Learning Discipline Factors in Class X Vocational School*

Students Sugiyono. 2011. *Educational Research Methods* .

Bandung: Alfabeta.2014.

Educational Research Methods, Quantitative Qualitative Approach, and R&D .

Bandung: PT Alfabet.2016. *Quantitative , Qualitative and R&D Research Methods* . Bandung: PT Alfabet.2017. *Quantitative, Qualitative and R&D*

Research Methods. Bandung: Alfabeta, CV.2018. *Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Research Methods* . Bandung: Alfabeta.2022. *Quantitative Research Methods* .Yogyakarta: Alfabeta

Purba, Siahaan, Sihombing

Tu'u, Sincere. 2004. The role of discipline on student behavior and achievement

.

Jakarta: Gramedia Widayarsana Indonesia.